

**APPROACHES TO THE NUMERICAL SOLUTION OF
DIFFERENTIAL EQUATIONS USING THE THEORY OF FUZZY SETS**

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Abstract. In this article, the numerical solution of ordinary differential equations is studied using the theory of fuzzy sets. Numerical solving of ordinary differential equations is aimed at finding exact numerical solutions, while numerical solving of such problems in fuzzy numbers allows finding intermediate solutions. Solving the ordinary differential equations in L-R type fuzzy numbers by the Cauchy problem imposed on the partial differential equation is studied. The article considers the application of the theory of fuzzy sets in the numerical solution of differential equations. They propose effective algorithms that demonstrate the applicability of fuzzy approaches in various fields, this paper will be useful for researchers involved in numerical analysis and modeling under uncertainty.

Keywords. Fuzzy number, algorithm, Cauchy problem, numerical solution, differential scheme, driving method, graphs.

1. Introduction. Mathematical theory of fuzzy sets proposed by Lotfiy Zade allows to describe fuzzy concepts and knowledge, to work with this knowledge and to draw vague conclusions. In recent years, the application of fuzzy control-fuzzy sets theory has been one of the most active and effective areas of research. In modern science and technology, the numerical solution of differential equations is a major problem facing researchers and engineers in various fields. This problem becomes

especially relevant in the problems of modeling dynamic systems, where exact analytical solutions do not exist or are difficult to obtain.

In recent decades, fuzzy set theory has attracted the attention of researchers as a powerful tool for describing uncertainty and closeness in data. In this context, the use of fuzzy approaches for the numerical solution of differential equations provides a promising way to account for uncertainty and uncertainty in dynamic process models. We consider methods of numerical solution of differential equations using the theory of fuzzy sets.

2. Method and model.

Algorithm for solving the differential equation with particular derivative using fuzzy sets

Example 1.

The following

$$\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} - \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} = 0 \tag{1}$$

$$u(x, 0) = 4x(1-x) \tag{2}$$

$$u(0, t) = u(1, t) = 0 \tag{3}$$

solve the boundary value problem by driving method as $h = 0,1$, $l = 0.01$

Solving. Since $h = 0,1$, $l = 0.01$ is $\alpha = \frac{l}{h^2} = 1$.

We transfer the given boundary value problem to a differential problem:

$$u_{i+1,j+1} - 3u_{i,j+1} + u_{i-1,j+1} + u_{i,j} = 0, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, 10; \quad j = 0, 1, 2, \dots,$$

$$u_{i0} = 4x_i(1-x_i)$$

$$u_{0j} = u_{10j} = 0$$

(1) according to the driving method

$$u_{i,j+1} = a_{i,j+1} (b_{i,j+1} + u_{i+1,j+1}) \tag{4}$$

is displayed, here $a_{i,j+1}, b_{i,j+1}$ quantities are determined in the following sequence:

$$a_{1,j+1} = \frac{1}{2+\alpha} = \frac{1}{3}$$

$$\begin{cases} a_{i,j+1} = \frac{1}{3-a_{i-1,j+1}} \\ b_{ij+1} = a_{i-1,j+1}b_{i-1,j+1} + u_{ij} \end{cases}$$

Then, since $u_{10,j+1} = 0$ is known from (3), $u_{i,j+1}$ from (4) is found as $i = 9, 8, \dots, 1$

Thus, if the values of $u(x, t)$ at t_j are known, then $t = t_{j+1}$ values in can be found by driving method.

Thus, in the first layer, the approximate values of the solution were found at the nodes. In the nodes of the next layer, the solution is found by performing these actions.

Example2. The following

$$\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} - \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} = 0 \tag{5}$$

$$u(x, 0) = \{0, 2; 0, 01; 0, 02\} x(1-x)\cos(\pi x), \quad \left. \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right|_{y=0} = 0 \tag{6}$$

$$u(0, y) = 0, \quad u(1, y) = 0 \tag{7}$$

Solve the boundary value problem by the grid method as $h = 0, 1, l = 0.01$
Solving. We transfer the differential problem to a discrete problem.

$$u_{i,j+1} = u_{i+1,j} + u_{i-1,j} - u_{i,j-1}, \tag{8}$$

$$u(x, 0) = \{0, 2; 0, 01; 0, 02\} x(1-x)\cos(\pi x), \quad \left. \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right|_{y=0} = 0 \tag{9}$$

$$u_{0,j} = 0, \quad u_{10,j} = 0. \tag{10}$$

We write the differential equation (8) at $j = 0$: $u_{i1} = u_{i+1,0} + u_{i-1,0} - u_{i,-1}$,

If we subtract $u_{i,-1}$ from this and the second of (9), we get $u_{i1} = \frac{u_{i+1,0} - u_{i-1,0}}{2}$.

The result is the following

$$\begin{cases} u_{i,j+1} = u_{i+1,j} + u_{i-1,j} - u_{i,j-1}, & j = 1, 2, 3, 4 \\ u_{i0} = 0, 2x_i(1 - x_i)\cos(\pi x_i), & u_{il} = \frac{u_{i+1,0} - u_{i-1,0}}{2}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, 9 \\ u_{0,j} = 0, & u_{10j} = 0, \quad j = 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 \end{cases}$$

we will have a system of differential equations. We place the calculation results in the table. u_{i0} to the first road of the table. We write the value of s , and in the second row we place the values of u_{i1} using the values from the first row. We determine those in the next layer using (8). Taking into account the symmetry of the problem, we present the result only for the interval $0 \leq x \leq 0,5$. Table 2.

Values of y_i corresponding to x_i

y_j/x_i	0	0,1	0,2	0,3	0,4	0,5
0	0	0,0056	0,0188	0,0340	0,0457	0,0500
1	0	0,0094	0,0198	0,0323	0,0420	0,0457
2l	0	0,0142	0,0229	0,0278	0,0323	0,0340
3l	0	0,0135	0,0222	0,0229	0,0198	0,0189
4l	0	0,0080	0,0135	0,0142	0,0095	0,0056
5l	0	0	0	0,0001	0	0,0001

Figures 1-4 show graphs corresponding to the main values of the function in blue, the left boundary of the fuzzy number in red, and the right boundary of the fuzzy number in green.

In these graphs we can see the dynamics of the left, right and main graphs of the function at different values of time.

Figure-1.t=0

Figure – 2. t=0,37

Figure-3. $t=0,74$

Figure-4. $t=1$

Conclusion.

The Cauchy problem applied to the partial differential equation using fuzzy numbers was solved numerically using the driving method. Left and right solutions of L-R type fuzzy numbers are obtained and graphs are drawn. In the presented graphs, the temporal evolution of the left, right, and principal graphs of the function is illustrated across various time instances.

These studies focus on the development of algorithms that take into account the ambiguity in discrete circuits, thereby providing more accurate methods for modeling systems with approximate and fuzzy information.

This study emphasizes the importance of considering fuzzy set theory in numerical solutions of differential equations, showcasing its potential to enhance computational models.

Future research can focus on refining and extending fuzzy set-based numerical methods to advance their applicability across scientific and engineering domains.

Overall, our findings contribute to the understanding of numerical methods employing fuzzy set theory, driving innovation in computational techniques for complex and uncertain dynamical systems.

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